

1 **HLA and HCG expression guides immune activation in utero during TE commitment.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 genes of the major histocompatibility (MHC) family as lineage commitment cooperating factors in
10 embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. The HLA-DRB family class II receptor was a component of
11 the TE transition, as was HCG15.

12 Citations

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1. Drukker, M., Katz, G., Urbach, A., Schuldiner, M., Markel, G., Itskovitz-Eldor, J., Reubinoff, B.,
Mandelboim, O. and Benvenisty, N., 2002. Characterization of the expression of MHC proteins in human
embryonic stem cells. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 99(15), pp.9864-9869.